

Crop and resource management

Plant physiology

Growth response of diverse rice genotypes to exogenous application of GA₃

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Although exogenous gibberellin (GA) usually breaks dwarfism, some cereal genotypes do not respond because they have a higher level of endogenous GA. This study examined the growth response to exogenous GA of rice genotypes with different statures and sources of dwarfism. The rice genotypes included a Dwarf mutant (superdwarf), dwarf Cigar, Nadula dwarf (semidwarf), Dee-geo-woo-gen (semi-dwarf), and C14-8 (tall). Seedlings (25 d old) were transplanted separately in the ricefield at 40- × 20-cm spacing during the wet season. A full dose of NPK was applied before transplanting

(during puddling). Two rows of each genotype were fully sprayed with 100 ppm of GA₃ at 20 and 45 d after planting. Morphological and growth characters were recorded at heading, and dry weights of plant parts were recorded after drying the plant samples in a hot air oven at 70 °C for 72 h.

Rice genotypes responded differently to exogenous GA₃ (Tables 1 and 2). The superdwarf Dwarf mutant reacted the most, by dwarf Cigar and semi-tall Dee-geo-woo-gen. The semidwarf line Nadula dwarf and tall cultivar C14-8 showed negligible growth response. GA₃ stimulated the vertical growth (height) in responsive genotypes, but suppressed their horizontal growth (tiller production, leaf breadth). Exogenous GA₃ caused drastic stimulation of leaf sheath, blade, lower (rudimentary) internodes, and panicle elongation in Dwarf mutant. This growth

enhanced the final stature of plants. GA₃ also caused greater enhancement in the size of individual leaf, leaf area per tiller and plant, and gravimetric growth of various plant parts (stem, leaf, and panicle) in GA₃-responsive genotypes. The ratio of leaf weight to total plant weight, leaf width, and tiller production were reduced markedly by exogenous GA₃ in responsive genotypes. GA₃ caused greater stimulation of stem growth than that of leaf growth (Table 2). In general, the morphological and growth effects of GA₃ were greater in dwarf genotypes than in semi-tall and tall ones, but an exception was noted in the semidwarf line Nadula dwarf. GA₃ enhanced the number of elongated internodes (mainly lower rudimentary) but not the total number of internodes per plant (Table 2). The elongation effect of GA₃ was greater in lower internodes than in upper internodes. ■

Table 1. Effect of exogenous GA₃ on morphological and growth characters of diverse rice varieties at heading.

Variety/ treatment	Plant height (cm)	Culm length (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Leaf area tiller ⁻¹ (cm ²)	Average length of leaf blade (cm)	Average width of leaf blade (cm)	Leaf weight ratio ^a	Dry weight plant ⁻¹ (g)				Dryweight tiller ⁻¹ (g)
									Stem	Leaf	Panicle	Total	
<i>Dwarf mutant</i>													
Control	54	42	12	32	117	20.4	1.69	0.35	15.1	12.1	7.2	348	1.08
GA ₃	123	105	18	24	211	41.5	1.29	0.20	48.8	16.1	8.8	79.5	3.31
% of control	230	251	151	75	180	203	76	57	323	323	122	228	306
<i>Cigar</i>													
Control	49	30	19	13	150	27.0	1.57	0.34	8.0	8.0	7.6	23.2	1.78
GA ₃	64	42	22	12	156	39.4	1.66	0.23	13.3	7.2	14.6	29.2	2.43
% of control	64	140	114	92	104	146	105	70	166	90	192	126	134
<i>Nadula dwarf</i>													
Control	75	58	17	12	509	51.0	2.28	0.31	43.1	25.3	12.0	80.4	6.70
GA ₃	77	60	17	11	471	58.4	2.01	0.30	38.9	22.2	13.0	79.0	6.72
% of control	103	104	100	92	92	114	88	97	90	88	108	92	100
<i>Dee-geo-woo-gen</i>													
Control	100	73	26	12	346	54.5	1.52	0.39	24.3	19.0	5.0	48.3	4.02
GA ₃	127	104	23	12	260	57.5	1.40	0.28	33.0	16.0	7.2	56.1	4.67
% of control	127	142	85	100	75	105	92	72	135	84	144	116	116
<i>C14-8</i>													
Control	188	159	29.0	12	480	71.0	1.60	0.24	76.7	29.1	13.4	131.6	10.0
GA ₃	202	172	29.0	13	441	75.0	1.65	0.25	95.3	37.5	17.4	150.0	11.6
% of control	107	108	100	108	92	106	103	104	124	128	130	126	116

^a Leaf weight
Total dry weight

Table 2. Effect of exogenous GA₃ on elongation of internodes and leaf sheath and expansion of leaf blade in rice varieties.

Variety/ treatment	Length of internode from top (cm)					Length of leaf sheath from top (cm)					Area of individual leaf from top (cm ²)				
	I	II	III	IV	V	I	II	III	IV	V	I	II	III	IV	V
<i>Dwarf mutant</i>															
Control	26	12	3	1	1	16	11	9	8	9	27	27	26	27	18
GA ₃	33	11	16	29	15	35	35	26	15	24	46	45	36	42	39
% of control	127	91	533	2900	1500	218	318	288	187	267	170	167	138	155	206
<i>Cigar</i>															
Control	16	10	3	1	1	20	12	12	11	9	48	47	33	22	15
GA ₃	18	13	6	3	2	23	14	10	14	10	55	55	41	19	-
% of control	112	130	200	200	200	115	117	83	127	111	114	117	124	86	-
<i>Nadula dwarf</i>															
Control	25	11	12	7	3	23	16	18	18	19	79	100	104	91	81
GA ₃	22	8	15	6	9	23	14	16	22	23	80	88	108	89	66
% of control	88	72	125	86	300	100	87	88	122	121	101	88	104	97	82
<i>Dee-geo-woo-gen</i>															
Control	31	14	16	8	6	36	26	27	23	26	56	80	79	67	46
GA ₃	30	16	18	30	10	35	34	26	24	24	49	76	66	57	56
% of control	96	114	112	275	150	97	130	96	104	92	87	95	83	85	121
<i>C14-8</i>															
Control	39	34	25	20	14	42	32	31	34	39	69	90	104	110	89
GA ₃	42	35	28	28	18	40	34	31	29	42	72	101	106	114	98
% of control	107	103	112	140	128	95	106	100	85	107	104	112	101	104	110

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of low light stress on photosynthesis, dry matter production, and grain yield in rice hybrids bred from two different cytoplasmic male sterile sources

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We compared the tolerance for low light of selected F₁ rice hybrids bred from two cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, IR62829A and IR58025A, during wet season in 1992 (see table). They were grown in 3-m² field plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing and fertilized with 60 kg N ha⁻¹. Wooden screens were used to create low light (50% of normal sun-light) from 35 d after transplanting until harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 340 cal cm⁻² d⁻¹). The split-plot design with three replications was used with the two light treatments in the main plots and the hybrids in the subplots. The photosynthetic rate (Pn) of the

Effect of shading on photosynthesis and yield in hybrids and restorers. Cuttack, India.^a

Hybrid/restorer	Pn (mg CO ₂ dm ⁻² h ⁻¹)		TDM (g m ⁻²)		Yield (g m ⁻²)		HI (%)	
	L	S	L	S	L	S	L	S
<i>Hybrids</i>								
IR62829 A/Swarna	41.6	29.1	1043	666	365	232	35	35
IR62829 A/Vajram	51.8	29.3	1377	818	665	269	48	33
IR58025 A/Swarna	51.6	29.2	952	582	356	167	38	35
IR58025 A/Vajram	37.4	25.4	947	695	352	176	37	26
<i>Restorers</i>								
Swarna	31.2	18.8	968	455	432	170	45	37
Vajram	48.5	30.7	1326	746	522	228	39	31
<i>Standard</i>								
Swarnaprabha	45.9	35.2	1141	703	520	218	46	31
Mean	44.0	28.2	1108	666	459	209	41	33
CD (5%)								
Variety (V)		0.71		54		22		3.4
Treatment (T)		4.36		54		24		2.3
V at same T		6.16		95		34		5.2
T at same V		5.77		76		45		4.8
<i>Heterosis (%) over restorer</i>								
IR62829 A/Swarna	33	55	8	46	-16	36	-22	-8
IR62829 A/Vajram	7	-5	4	10	27	18	26	6
IR58025 A/Swarna	51	55	-2	28	-18	-2	-15	-8
IR58025 A/Vajram	-23	-17	-29	-7	-33	-23	-5	-16
Mean	17	22	-5	19	-10	7	-4	-7

^aPn = photosynthetic rate, TDM = total dry matter, HI = harvest index, L = light, S = shaded.